

Minting. Mining cryptos is not the only way to get coins.

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Mining cryptocurrency (aka Proof of Work (PoW)) has been considered the only method of creating coin into existence. But there is another method called Minting or Proof of Stake (PoS) that doesn't require GPU or expensive mining equipment and huge electricity bills.

2. Aim

To familiarize with alternative coin creation methods = Proof of Work vs. Proof of Stake methods.

3. Material and Methods

AAA COIN is used as an alternative coin (altcoin) example for Proof of Stake.

4. Results & Discussion

AAA COIN was created to test the Proof of Stake coin minting scenario and was successful in creating market for it, minting new coin, and listing it on exchange to freely exchange between a number of well established cryptocurrencies.

5. Conclusions

Minting coin or Proof of Stake method is a cheap and widely available method for creating coin compared to Mining or Proof of Work method popularized by Bitcoin. No GPU or special miners are required, no staggering electricity bills.

6. Keywords

AAA COIN, bitcoin, altcoin, crypto, pos, pow, proof of work, proof of stake, mining, minting

7. Authors' contributions

AAA COIN Whitepaper, Alex Povolotski, 2017 <http://aaacoin.us>

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